

WHY SPEAKING SKILL IS IMPORTANT IN HIGHER EDUCATION.

Bahromova Munisa Otabekovna

Termez State University Foreign Philology Faculty the 2nd course student.

@munisabahromova1@gmail.com , +99890 644 79 09

Abstract: In this article, the concept of speech culture and its importance in higher education is discussed. Higher education today speech should be clear and concise, strictly ordered, understandable for everyone. Own the words Using it instead increases the effectiveness of the word, quickly conveying the essence of the story serves to get.

Key words: Speaking, micro-skills, communicating messages, social language.

Speaking is considered to be the most important active skill for a foreign language learning. It is producing utterances for communicating messages. It starts from infancy to be developed during childhood to maturity. Speaking as a collection of micro-skills which include syntax, grammar, morphology, pragmatics or social language, semantics and phonology. Speaking is an interactive process because it requires the involvement of another person unlike listening, reading or writing . Speaking skill isn't only producing the utterances, but it is the complete process of constructing meanings, producing utterances and receiving and processing information with confidence. The meaning formation depends on the context, purpose, subject matter of the speech and the speaker's personality and the physical environment of the situation. It also includes the participants, their relationship, their cultural backgrounds, and their experience in the topic. We need speaking for many reasons; educators, governments, ministries of education and employers need people who can speak English well. Companies and organizations want staff who can speak English for international marketing. Good English speaking students have a great chance of further education, of finding employment and gaining promotion . It also helps students to access up-to-date information in different fields of sciences.

Speech is a unique tool called language that performs very important tasks the process of use, the existence of the possibilities of language units, thinking, consciousness and is manifested in relation to events such as situations. Speech is language in action and appears during the movement of speech organs and word forms, word consists of combinations and sentences. Speech culture, the desire to speak culturally concept is a long-standing phenomenon in all vernacular languages. This concept is known a concept related to linguistic standards, ethical and aesthetic requirements is considered

Speaking is not merely a matter of using words, but it needs a more complicated process of producing speech. Speaking is a productive skill that needs a lot of practices. In addition to listening, speaking is mostly taught to the students before reading and writing. By using spoken English, the students will be able to convey their idea. Therefore, speaking is a direct route from one mind to another and is the best way to ask a question or give an explanation. In one way, English is the language which connects people from different regions, cultures, religions, and nations. Brown and Lee claim that “English is increasingly being used as a tool for interaction among nonnative speakers”. Among the four language skills, speaking seems to play more important role in communication. Chastain views speaking “as one important element in developing each language skill and conveying culture knowledge”. Considering the significance of accuracy, more attention is drawn to fluency in achieving communicative purposes in conversations.

It is also a good opportunity for students from different backgrounds to participate and exchange experiences and cultural aspects. ♣ Classrooms should be equipped with all facilities for learners of a second language while students collaborate and communicate ideas and information. Students should work in pairs, small groups, or large groups to enhance the purposes of speaking tasks.

♣ Timing is crucial for practicing speaking activities, thinking of the situations, and the uses of the language functions in the real wide world.

♣ Teacher's roles are important as he is the one who is responsible for: - Giving students the opportunities to collect information, and interpret the information they collect. - Building the new knowledge upon students' prior knowledge by reconstructing and reshaping prior understanding. - Finding different styles of questions to elicit answers and read pictures and enhance students' responses. - Encouraging purposeful talk and tentative "thinking aloud". - Focusing his reaction on the intention of students' responses rather than grammar and dialect. - Constructing and developing a variety of assessment types to guarantee involvement of students in different speaking activities. - Encouraging peer assessment that focuses on strengths and areas for improvement. - Valuing questions as much as answers. - Sharing enthusiasm for telling stories to students and by providing opportunities for students to tell stories. - Making informal talks and sharing facts and opinions as a regular part of the program. - Encouraging students to challenge their own and others' assumptions, prejudices, and information presented as facts. - Promoting students' abilities to develop and participate during discussions and debates. - Developing students' respect to others' feelings, opinions, ethics, cultural diversity. - Setting personal goals for communicating appropriately and effectively, and for understanding the needs of listeners and participants. -

Respect cultural traditions. - Encouraging and appreciating efforts and improvement as well as competence. - Assessing both processes and products. Speaking requires that learners know how to produce the linguistic competence e.g. grammar, pronunciation, or vocabulary.

Likewise, speaking skills empower human to create new ways of speaking to others about any topic or experience. To speak fluently, correctly with proper intonation and pronunciation especially in the second or foreign language adds to credit of the speaker. The excellence in the use of the ability to speak in second language makes the speaker a skilful communicator. Effective Communication skill is one of the standards for the teachers in many countries of world .Indeed, second language follows the same pattern of learning as the first language follows: preproduction (the learner only listens), early production (can use short language chunks), speech emergence (they try to initiate short conversation with friends), intermediate fluency and advanced fluency (the students are nearly-native in their ability). Use of target language to talk about language is the best strategy for learning spoken language. Teacher education programs need to be strengthened for effective oral English instruction and assessment .

References

1. Conversations about a foreign language lesson: for students of pedagogical institutes manual / Passov E.I., Kolova T.I., Volkova T.A., Dobronravova T.N., Voronova O.M., Krainova E.A. - L., "Education", - 1975.
2. Bim I.L. On the issue of the methodology of teaching foreign languages. // IYaSh.-1974.- No. 2.-S.19-32.
3. Volovin A.V. Foreign languages in British and American methodological systems Communicative approach to learning // Communicative approach to learning foreign languages approach: collection of articles. scientific. works, volume 275 - M., 1985.
4. Introduction to the communicative methodology of teaching English: Russian teachers guide to -Oxford University Press, 1997.